

Unveiling the Working-from-Home Gender Disparity: An Investigation of Sri Lankan IT Professionals

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Abstract

The shift to new work models like working-from-home, particularly during the pandemic, has blurred the boundaries between work and home. The impact on work and life routines seems to generate vital implications for gender equality. Traditional, patriarchal gender norms such as good girl, loyal wife and family honour and discriminatory practices such as expectation for women to become full-time housewives sacrificing their educational and occupational ambitions have placed women in a vulnerable position. In this context, understanding how working-from-home is perceived differently by women and men in the IT field, where remote work is highly feasible, becomes crucial against the backdrop of gendered patterns prevalent in social structures at work and at home. This paper, therefore, aims to explore the experiences of gender relations of women and men in the IT sector in Sri Lanka, where traditional patriarchal values persist and economic struggles prevail, as they shifted to working-from-home. The following research questions are addressed: (1) What is the gendered nature of the IT profession in Sri Lanka? (2) How is the pandemic-induced work-from-home experience perceived by IT professionals? (3) How does gender disadvantage operate among IT professionals working from home? (4) What is the nature of the gendered impact of working from home on work-life balance and well-being for male and female IT professionals? (5) What are the recommendations that could be proposed for policymakers and practitioners to facilitate gender equality, employee well-being, and work-life balance for IT professionals working from home? A qualitative research approach is adopted, involving 50 in-depth interviews with IT professionals who are currently working-from-home or in hybrid work arrangements, followed by a thematic analysis to generate insights from their experiences.

Keywords: working-from-home; gender; information technology sector; Sri Lanka

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Overview

This paper explores the gendered nature IT professionals' work-from-home experiences in Sri Lanka given its conventional, gendered, household structures, cultural norms and the patterns of employment.

Background

During pre-industrial times work and family were one consolidated production unit, and later in industrial societies, a clear division between work and family spheres was developed. Over time, changing socio-economic, technological and rising demands and complexities associated within working lives required the organization of work to be adjusted to facilitate better work-life balance (Papalexandris and Kramar, 1997), flexible working arrangements were thus designed. The modern IT workplace encourages the new work culture of working-from-home and hybrid work arrangements. Working-from-home is argued to be blurring the boundaries between work and life worlds with gendered experiences and implications. The notable shift to work-from-home during the pandemic had the potential to significantly shape and transform traditional gendered patterns of behaviour in the household (Shockley et al., 2021). However, a regression to customary gendered patterns to manage work and family domains is noted as women were increasingly reported to reallocate the flexibility in their work to meet household and family demands, thereby internalizing gendered patterns and upholding the traditional division of labor within households (Chung et al., 2021). Globally, research during and post-pandemic era reports that women reassumed traditional gender identities and share increased, uneven and additional household burdens of caring for children, caring for the sick, caring for the elderly as well as sharing household labour (Power, 2020). When work-from-home arrangements do not factor in perspectives of gender roles, it can further widen gender gaps and place women in a more disadvantageous, vulnerable position, with losing their emancipatory prospects of work and careers and fulfilling lives.

Predominantly gender related problems encountered by women take diverse forms across different cultures and life conditions (Parlak, Cakiroglu, and Gul, 2021). In Sri Lanka, despite the extension of women's economic roles, in the household inequitable gender division of labor has only dimly transformed (ADB, 1999). Though education and employment indicators place Sri Lankan women in a better position in the South Asian region, patriarchal forms of organization persist (Hapke, 2013), and patronizing gender ideologies such as good women, good girl and loyal wife (Jayawardena, 2018; Wimalasena, 2017) that impact adversely on women are still predominant (ADB, 1999). Thereby this study focusses on reflecting on the experiences of women and men working-from-home in the IT sector, against the unique Sri Lankan context.

Current Achievements

Data collection through in depth interviews is currently in progress. Target individuals, who have switched to working-from-home with the pandemic mandates and continued to work in either pure work-from-home or hybrid work arrangements during the time of interviewing, are reached through purposive sampling and snowballing. Currently we are in the process conducting the remaining interviews with the assistance of the Sri Lanka Association of Software and Service Companies.

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